

Local Government Autonomy in India, the United States of America and Australia: A Comparative Study

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Abstract

This research paper provides a comparative study of the autonomy of local governments in the United States, Australia, and India. These three countries are federal, but with historical development, their local governments have varied based on constitutional and legal basis, political autonomy, administrative autonomy, and financial autonomy. The Constitutions of the United States and Australia do not mention local governments. Two forms of local government exist in the United States: Dillon Law states and Home Rule states. In Home Rule states, local governments have considerable political, administrative, and financial autonomy. They also have the power to enact local laws. The United States is quite good in terms of administrative autonomy. Local governments have complete control over local personnel and administration. Financial position is also quite good. In six US states combined, local governments derive approximately 80% of their revenue from their own sources. In Australia, local government powers exist, but they are controlled by the state government. In Australia, local governments have substantial executive powers. They have complete control over personnel administration. In Australia, local governments generate approximately 80% of their revenue from their own sources. In India, although local governments are mentioned in the Constitution, their political, administrative, and financial autonomy is not good. They neither have the power to make laws nor the power to appoint their own employees. Their financial situation is also not good. Local self-governments in India still have a lot of work to do in the field of autonomy. Compared to the US, their autonomy is very limited, and even when compared to Australia, their autonomy appears to be less.

Key words: Local Autonomy, Home rule, Dillo's law, Political Autonomy, Administrative Autonomy, Local Government in USA, Local Government in India.

Introduction

Local government not only serves as the third tier of government in Indian politics, but also represents democratic decentralization. This system increases people's participation in governance and allows them to directly participate in local affairs, thereby establishing true democracy. The development of local government has historically varied across countries. Here, we will study the autonomy of local self-government in India, the United States of America, and Australia. The United States and Australia are developed countries, while India is a developing country. These three countries gained independence from British colonial rule and are federal, but variations exist in local self-government in all three countries. The primary objective of this study is to compare local governance in these three countries and draw conclusions about India's position in terms of the level of autonomy.

Research Methodology

This study used a comparative analysis method, which is qualitative and descriptive in nature. The study examined the autonomy of local self-government in the United States, Australia, and India through the following dimensions:

1. Constitutional and Legal Basis
2. Political Autonomy

3. Administrative Autonomy
4. Financial Autonomy

Secondary sources such as books, research papers, and journal articles were used as sources of data.

Conceptual Framework: Local Autonomy

To understand local autonomy, it is essential to understand its difference from local democracy. Local democracy reflects the participation of local citizens in local governance and makes local government accountable. Local autonomy refers to the independent decision-making ability of local government and freedom from interference from higher governments. Local autonomy primarily consists of two components (Grant & Drew.2017):

1. **Immunity** - This reflects the absence of external interference or interference from higher governments (Grant & Drew.2017).
2. **Initiative** - Freedom to make any kind of decision and formulate policy (Grant & Drew.2017).
Immunity and initiative, taken together, reveal that autonomy refers to decision-making and implementation in the absence of external pressure. Autonomy in local self-government means that the local government faces neither pressure nor interference from the central or state governments in discharging its responsibilities, meaning that it has complete freedom to make any kind of decision, formulate policy, and implement it to discharge its functions and responsibilities.

Local Self-Government in the United States

There is no provision of local government in United States Constitution. The central government cannot enact laws establishing local governments. In such a situation, states can establish local governments by mentioning them in their constitutions or by enacting laws. In the United States, local governments are mentioned in the constitutions or laws of the state governments. The current autonomy of local governments in the United States has a history that is linked to Dillon's Law and Home Rule.

1. Dillon's Law

Before 1868, corruption in local governments in the United States was rampant. The judiciary intervened due to increasing financial risks. Judge John F. Dillon established state government control over municipalities, clarifying that municipalities would have only those powers that the state government would determine and specify in the constitution or law (Grant & Drew.2017).

2. Home Rule

Over time, growing cities began challenging Dillon's Law. This demand for autonomy prompted state legislatures to enact home rule charters. After persistent efforts, Missouri became the first state to recognize home rule for local governments in its constitution. Subsequently, 13 states incorporated home rule provisions into their constitutions. To establish Home Rule, the constitutions of these thirteen states included a provision that local issues would be governed by the charters, which would be approved by a vote of the local people, in one case by the city council. (Grant & Drew.2017,p-200). This autonomy grants them the power to make laws and levy taxes.

The federal structure of the United States has three levels. The federal government is followed by the state government, but the state government is not subordinate to the central government but functions independently. Local governments operate under the state government. The United States Constitution is called a constitution of grants because it clearly outlines the powers of the federal government. State governments have all powers except those granted to the federal government. These powers can only be limited by amending the Constitution, so state constitutions can be called constitutions of limitations. States are divided into various divisions, commonly called counties. In Louisiana, this is called a parish, and in Alaska, it is called a borough. A county is a large administrative structure primarily responsible for important matters such as law and order, tax collection, and health. Within it are units such as cities, villages, towns, and townships. Cities, villages, towns, and townships operate independently, but some vital services, such as jails, courts, and health, are provided by the county. In the United States, the appointment, transfer, and dismissal of local government employees is done by the county government; the state government has no role in this.

County Structure

In the United States, every county has its own board or council. Board members or councilors are directly elected by the public. Three types of county forms are found in the United States.

1. Commission Form

This form has a central board called the Board of Commissioners/Board of Supervisors/County Court, whose members are directly elected by the public. It makes policy decisions (passing budgets and ordinances) and also administers them. Each board member is the executive head of a department. There is no mayor or chief executive officer(Kemp.2002).

2. Commission-Administrator Form

In this type of system, a professional administrator is appointed by the board/council, who is responsible for managing the county's affairs and implementing policies(Kemp.2002).

3. Council-Elected Executive Form

In this type of system, the chief executive officer is directly elected by the public, making this position quite powerful. The council formulates county policies, while the chief executive officer implements them. The executive branch is headed by the chief executive officer. (Kemp.2002)

City Structure

At the city level, we see five forms.

1. Mayor-Council Form

In this system, the mayor and council members are directly elected by the public. However, in some states, the mayor's position is strong, while in others, it is weak. In states where the mayor's position is strong, the mayor holds significant executive powers, such as budget control, appointment of city officials and employees, and the power to veto ordinances. In a weak mayor system, all these powers are vested in the council (Kemp.2002).

2. Council-Manager Form

In this system, the public-elected council appoints a manager who oversees the city's day-to-day operations and implements policies(Kemp.2002).

3. Commission Form

In this system, the public directly elects a commission that formulates and implements city policies. Each member of the commission is the executive head of a department. There is no mayor or chief executive officer in this system(Kemp.2002).

4. Town Meeting Form

This type of town is found in small towns in New England. All the voters constitute the town's legislature, which meets once a year to make decisions through direct voting. This assembly has the power to make bylaws, levy taxes, and allocate funds for the town. During the rest of the year, day-to-day operations are run by an elected select board(Kemp.2002).

5. Representative Town Meeting Form

This is a modified form of the town meeting. Both the public and their elected representatives attend the town meeting, but only the representatives have the right to vote(Kemp.2002).

Special Purpose District

This type of local body is created for a specific purpose, such as education, fire protection, or water supply etc. Its functions are managed by a board. Sometimes, state governments exercise their legal authority to create special-purpose districts to efficiently deliver certain services at the regional level. Public education districts are funded by local property taxes and state funding(Steytler. 2024).

Financial Condition

The main tax sources for local governments in the United States are income tax, property tax, and special sales taxes. In nine states, local governments do not levy income tax (Steytler. 2024,p-513). The

financial situation of local governments in the United States is quite good. According to the US Census Bureau report (Analysis of the Census of Governments (2017)), approximately 73.9% of total state revenue of local government in Illinois, 80.8% in Indiana, 77.2% in Michigan, 83.2% in Minnesota, 87.4% in Ohio, and 78.8% in Wisconsin comes from own sources (tax and non-tax revenue) (Kass, Rocco, & Romano. 2021,p-7). Collectively, these six states account for approximately 80% of revenue from their own resources. Approximately 20% of revenue comes from grants from the federal and state governments. Despite being a significant tax source, local governments face significant workload pressures. On one hand, they have important subjects like law and order, public works and fire protection, while on the other hand, they have to work under the funded and unfunded mandate of the central and state governments. Under the funded mandate, the state and central governments provide funds for their work, whereas under the unfunded mandate, no funds are provided for implementing their laws. To carry out these tasks, a large amount of financial resources along with human resources are spent.

Local Self-Government in Australia

The Australian Constitution of 1901 does not mention local government. State governments have enacted their own laws to establish local governments. Local bodies in Australia primarily include city councils for urban areas, town councils for smaller cities, shire councils for villages, and regional councils representing larger areas that are comprised of several local units. Within a city's structure, we see three main components:

1. **Mayor** - In some states, the mayor is directly elected by the public, while in others, the council itself elects the mayor.
2. **Council** - The council is composed of councilors directly elected by the public.
3. **Chief Executive** - Appointed by the council.

The personnel administration of local government falls under the Chief Executive Officer. They have the authority to recruit, appoint, and dismiss personnel. They oversee day-to-day operations and policy implementation. The Chief Executive Officer is accountable to the council, not the state government. Local governments in Australia can pass bylaws or ordinances, but they do not have full law-making power. These bylaws and ordinances are also made under the rules of the state government, which the state government can repeal or amend at any time. Local governments have limited functional powers. They primarily provide services such as roads, waste management, water and sewerage, community services, urban planning, health and the environment. They do not have police and fire services. There is no reservation of any kind. Property taxes are the main source of revenue for local governments in Australia. Fees for services such as drainage and waste management are also sources of revenue. Parking fees, library fees, and other fees are also sources of revenue. Local governments here derive approximately 80% of their total expenditure from their own sources (Steytler. 2024,p-60), such as taxes, charges, fees and investments, and approximately 20% of their revenue comes from federal and state government grants.

Local Self-Government in India

Local government in India was granted constitutional status by the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments, creating a uniform structure across the country. The 73rd Constitutional Amendment created a three-tier structure at the village, block, and district levels. Elections at all three levels are conducted through both direct and indirect means. In some states, the village head is directly elected, while in others, the sarpanch is indirectly elected by the panchayats. At the block level, members are directly elected by the public, while the chairperson is indirectly elected by the members. At the district council level, members are directly elected, while the chairperson is indirectly elected. At the executive level, officials at all three levels are appointed by the state government: the Village Development Officer at the village level, the Block Development Officer at the block level, and the Chief Executive Officer at the district level. Other employees at these three levels are also appointed by the state government.

The financial resources of Panchayati Raj institutions in India are very limited. Approximately 80 to 95 percent of their total revenue is derived from loans and grants-in-aid from the central and state governments (Steytler. 2024,p-266). Due to their financial dependence, they have to function under the guidelines of the state and central governments. Another issue is that panchayats do not have independent authority on any subject; they can only perform tasks as determined by the state government. The state determines the jurisdiction of panchayats on which subjects, the taxes that local governments can impose, and their limits.

The 74th Constitutional Amendment created three main forms of urban government: Nagar Panchayats, Nagar Palikas, and Municipal Corporations. The governing head of these Nagar Panchayats and Nagar Palikas is the Chairman of the Council, who is directly elected by the people, and the executive head is the Executive Officer in a Nagar Panchayat, and the Chief Executive Officer in a Nagar Palika. The governing head of a Municipal Corporation is called the Mayor, who is directly elected by the people in some states and indirectly by the Council in others. The executive head of a Corporation is the Municipal Commissioner, who is appointed by the State Government. There are two main models of Mayor in India.

1. Bombay System

According to the Bombay Municipal Corporation Act of 1888, the executive power of the corporation is vested in the Commissioner. The Commissioner is appointed by the state government. Deliberative power lies within the Council and its standing committees. In this system, the Commissioner has greater power than the Mayor(Steytler. 2024).

2. Kolkata Model

Under the Kolkata Municipal Corporation Act 1980, the corporation consists of a council called the Mayor-in-Council. There are three organs: the Council, the Mayor-in-Council, and the Mayor. The Mayor-in-Council has executive power, while the Municipal Commissioner does not(Steytler. 2024).

The 74th Constitutional Amendment defined 18 functions for municipal governments under the 12th Schedule, but it is up to the state governments to decide how many functions they delegate to them. No state has assigned all 18 subjects to the municipal government. In Karnataka, the local municipal government has been assigned only three of these 18 subjects (Steytler. 2024). Urban local bodies can only discuss and interpret the assigned functions. They do not have any legislative powers. The state government also has complete control over the appointment of employees in municipal bodies. The state government has the authority to select and appoint officers of the provincial municipal services, meaning that Group A and B officers are appointed by the state government. Group C and D employees are appointed by the local government only if this authority is granted by the state government. In this regard, the local government must follow the rules made by the state government.

Financial Sources

The main financial sources of municipal governments are property taxes,entertainment taxes, sewerage charges, water charges, etc. The financial condition of urban local bodies is poor. Urban local bodies have very limited tax sources. A large portion of their expenditures are funded by central and state grants. During the period from 2014/15 to 2018/19, local bodies' revenue from their own financial resources never exceeded 50%. The highest revenue achieved during 2018/19 was only 41%.. The highest revenue received was only 41% in 2018/19(Steytler. 2024,p-267).

Analysis of Local Autonomy

1. Constitutional and Legal Basis

The Constitutions of the United States and Australia do not mention local government. States can establish local governments in their constitutions or through charters. The Indian Constitution contains provisions related to local self-government.

2. Political Autonomy

In states where Home Rule Law exists in the United States, local governments enjoy considerable freedom and autonomy. They have broad authority to formulate policies and laws within their jurisdiction. In states where Dillon Law exists, local governments do not have the power to formulate policies and laws independently; they can only perform those functions that have been authorized by the state legislature through legislation. Local governments can enact by-laws or ordinances, which must then be approved by the state government. The situation in Australia is similar to that of the Dillon Law states in the United States. In India, local governments do not have the power to enact laws. They can exercise only those powers delegated to them by the state government. In all three countries, local council or board members are directly elected by the public, while mayors are elected both directly and indirectly.

3. Administrative Autonomy

In the United States, officials such as the county administrator/manager and city manager are appointed by the local government. Here, other employees are also recruited by the local government. In Australia, the CEO is appointed by the local government, and other employees are appointed by the CEO. In India, the corporation commissioner, municipal chief executive officer, and town council executive officer are appointed by the state government, and other employees are also generally appointed by the state government.

In the United States, local governments have extensive functional powers. They cover key areas such as police, education, health, and fire protection services. In Australia, local governments have limited municipal services. The 11th and 12th Schedules of the Indian Constitution specify prescribed functions, but no state has delegated full determinative functions to local governments. While limited intervention in local government administration is observed in the United States, extensive control is observed in Australia. In India, the state government exercises direct control over local government.

4. Financial Autonomy

In six states of the United States America, approximately 80% of local government revenue comes from its own sources (Kass, Rocco, & Romano. 2021). In the United States, local bodies also collect essential taxes, such as income tax. In Australia, approximately 80% of local government revenue comes from its own sources (Steytler. 2024,p-60). In India, this figure is less than 50% (Steytler. 2024,p-267). The financial situation of rural local bodies is very poor.

Conclusion

Although local governments in India have constitutional status, their autonomy is poor. State control prevails, whether it's the appointment of employees or the financial condition of local governments. In India, the position of Municipal Commissioners, Chief Executive Officers, and Executive Officers is quite strong. Since they are appointed by the state government, conflicts within the body are common, as they vest all administrative power within them. The Kolkata model of autonomy is slightly better, as it vests all executive power in the Mayor-in-Council. In the United States, local governments have been given significant responsibilities, such as police, but in India, even the delegated subjects are not fully delegated. While the financial situation of local governments in the United States and Australia is quite good, the situation of urban governments in India is poor. The financial situation of rural self-governments is extremely poor. In the United States, most states also collect important taxes, such as income tax. From a comprehensive study of autonomy, it can be concluded that local government autonomy in the United States is much greater in Home Rule states. While local governments in Australia may not have constitutional status, their status is better than in India. In India, the autonomy of local self-government depends entirely on the will, financial resources, and political culture of the state. To enhance autonomy, it is necessary to increase financial resources, grant local self-government powers such as the appointment and transfer of employees, and fully allocate the functions entrusted to them by the Constitution.

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